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TECHNOLOGIES OF CONSTRUCTION OF AUTOMOBILE ROADS FROM PLASTIC WASTE

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Anatation: This article discusses issues such as modern road surface preparation technology, waste problem, improvement and efficient use of waste recycling.

Keywords: *bitumen, waste, plastic, ocean, UN, degree, percentage, local, asphalt concrete, cement concrete.*

Introduction

There are a number of problems and shortcomings in the system of state management of the road sector of the republic, which hinder the formation of a competitive environment and investment in the sector. In order to create a modern system of road management, clear delimitation of control and economic functions, de-monopolization, attract private sector enterprises and increase investment attractiveness, create a healthy competitive environment, the widespread introduction of innovations in road construction, Also, in accordance with the objectives of the Action Strategy for the five priority areas of development of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2017-2021, on December 9, 2019, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan issued a decree "On measures to deep reform the road sector of the Republic of Uzbekistan The resolution "On measures to further improve the management system of the road sector" was adopted.[1]

MAIN PART

Today, the world's waste is increasing year by year. Every year, plastic waste dumped into rivers pollutes and kills not only the riverbeds, but also the world's oceans by flowing through the rivers into the oceans. Plastic waste falling into the oceans gets into the stomachs of various rare animals and then causes them to die. Therefore, one of the solutions to the problem is to reduce plastic waste. We promoted another industry as a recycled material. We got an used product from an industry. As a result, we have not only solved the problem of tire destruction, but also reduced the carbon footprint of the concrete industry [2]. Another innovation in the industry is the installation of colored plastic barriers on both sides of the road. The product is based on South Korean technology at the Korean Trans joint venture. This building material, which has already been tested abroad and is widely used, does not lag behind metal barriers in terms of strength and durability. As plastic waste increases, plastic roads are being created for recycling. Interestingly, these plastic roads are not only environmentally friendly, but also beneficial in other ways. It is far superior to our asphalt roads in terms of use. Plastic is resistant to corrosion and atmospheric pressure and is effective in conditions from -40 degrees to +80 degrees [5,6].

Today, we see a man walking on a modern road across the Chirchik River, excitedly talking about how far it is, how fast and easy it is to get to the destination. In particular, the 6.5-kilometer bike path and sidewalks built along the main road have created great convenience for the residents of the area. Plastic barriers at the edges serve to protect against various accidents.

CONCLUSION

Today, there are shortcomings and inconveniences in the field of road construction and operation in the country: the lack of bitumen, outdated technology, the complexity of cement concrete technology. When cracks appear in waste coatings, the fibers tend to have a much higher resistance to cracking and cracking. As a result, the cracks become narrower and the coating lasts longer.

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